

8T – The Coupling Constants Series is Continuous and Discrete

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants main features, it is possible to classify and emphasize the continuous features of the series and alongside the discrete features of the series, such as the net curvature that are discrete amounts isomorphic to prime numbers or one. Analysis regarding the amount of gauge fields mediating an interaction is presented, and a take on additional set of constants similar to plank constant, one for each higher term in the series.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard bosons as net curvature on the matric tensor. The net curvature are of discrete amounts and is isomorphic to the prime numbers or one. From the weak interaction and above the symmetry is broken to an additional element in the coupling term, i.e. the majestic three. Each boson has a unique discrete number, as presented in equation (1.21) and that is synonymous with the idea behind the Planck constant. That is the major feature of the series that is discrete.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.21)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (1.3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (1.32)$$

The discrete feature of the series indicate that for each higher term there could be a constant unique to its magnitude of net curvature, similar to the Planck constant for the third term. That is in agreement with the overall idea of the 8T, infinite amount of coupling constants. Interesting question regarding the actual value of each coupling term. The net curvature is increasing in magnitude but each coupling term is weak than its preceding. So, in physical terms, does that mean each physical constant that is analogous to Planck is smaller or larger in value?

The continuous part of the series is quite vivid, as analyzed before, each element is a result of the preceding. That is due to the even sum of the preceding element. That is mainly the idea behind the arrow of time, and the statement that the direction of the series is the direction of time as presented in the 8T thesis. Additional point regarding the continuous feature of the series is that many interactions can appear that the same part of the matrix tensor of the same time. that is to say, many bosons, or net curvatures of certain magnitude can occupy the same space. these can be polarized linearly or circularly, and each net curvature is increasing the probability of arrival to its position.

The image above is the representation of the above claims. The bosons manifestations are continuous despite the fact they are represented in a form of a discrete number. Bosons are net curvature diverging and spinning, a curvature cortexes of certain magnitude which could vary in diameter overtime, as the author believes. The most important feature that is continuous is the setting of the theory, which is the varying connected manifold with (3,1) signature. The manifold was invoked stationary to provide us the main equation, which is a describing a continuous variation of the matrix tensor over time, given by the main equation (2).

$$s = (M, g)$$

$$\mathcal{L} = (s, s', t)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} - \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right) \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0, \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

These are the major features of the series in the 8T that are continuous. Analysis of the continuous features versus the discrete features is interesting as many physicists and mathematicians argued whether the fundamental laws of physics are continuous or discrete. As it turns out, they are a morphism between discrete and continuous. Both views are correct. That is supported by the fact that we have constants of nature, such as the Planck constant, and the fact that theories of physics are described on continuous and connected settings, such as the connected manifold. In addition to Einstein theory which has a certain degree of accuracy and correctness despite not taking into consideration the short range of gravity.

References

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- [3] O. Manor. "Proving Einstein Wrong – Gravity is a Short Range Interaction" In: (2021)